

Teaching Controversial Issues in Social Studies Class to Develop Critical Thinking and Social Analysis Ability

Arif Purnomo, Wasino, Tri Marhaeni Pudji Astuti, Suyahmo

Postgraduate Programmes, Universitas Negeri Semarang, Semarang, Indonesia.

Corresponding Author: Arif Purnomo

ABSTRACT

Social studies learning so far have not been oriented to the development of critical thinking skills and social analysis; teachers are often stuck in the formal charges related to learning rather than creativity in developing an interesting learning. The objective of this research is to analyze the implementation of controversial learning material on social studies subjects in an effort to develop critical thinking and social analysis ability of students which conducted in secondary schools. This research was conducted using Creswell's framework, namely the study of phenomenology in qualitative research. The data source of this research came from secondary school social studies teachers in Semarang as informants, both in the interview and observation sessions during the teacher's teaching. Analysis of the data in this research refers to the framework of Creswell's phenomenological data analysis, which explains the data analysis techniques in the study of phenomenology. The results of this research are as follows: 1) the lesson plan that carried out is still conventional and teachers are still chained by formal demands to complete responsibilities, not develop the knowledge; 2) learning controversial issues are still not optimal, a social studies teachers have not been put dialogue as a force in the development of critical thinking and social analysis ability of the student; and 3) the evaluation carried out is not yet sufficiently developed to measure students' critical thinking skills and social analysis after participating in learning controversial issues. The implication of this research is that teachers must broaden their horizons, deepen the material to be taught, improvise in the use of media, learning resources, methods, and approaches,

and make relevant evaluation instruments, thus learning controversy material in social studies classes will lead to the development of critical thinking and social analysis ability of the students.

Keywords: Social Studies, Controversial Issues, Critical Thinking, Social Analysis

INTRODUCTION

Social studies learning in Indonesia so far have not yet led to the development of students' critical thinking and social analysis ability. ⁽¹⁾ This is influenced by material and teaching processes factors in the classroom that have not implemented dialogical learning methods and models yet. During this time, learning still uses lecture methods that are one-way and do not develop the ability of students personally. This problem is more interesting to discuss after King in his research put forward findings which stating that social studies learning has not had a strong foundation in terms of the curriculum, especially in an effort to develop critical thinking and social analysis ability owned by students, ⁽²⁾ although it is still a hypothesis, research conducted in the West is the result of study related to social studies education policy that focuses on aspects of nationalism and development of a national awareness. Such learning does not violate the rules of knowledge, but in terms of education need to be questioned again about the ability of learning policies oriented to the growth of nationalism can accommodate efforts to

develop critical thinking skills and social analysis in students' personal, as the essence of social studies learning stated by Barr that social studies learning at the secondary school level is no longer doctrinal in nature, but students are able to contextualize the thoughts they have acquired in learning critically and analytically, so that in the process new knowledge will be found that provides stock for social life. ⁽³⁾

Controversial learning material in social studies is one of the alternative ways that teachers can do to develop students' critical thinking and social analysis abilities. During this time, learning controversial material is often ignored and not taught seriously by the teacher in the classroom. ^(4,5) The reason is that the teacher does not have enough knowledge to teach the material that requires thinking, methods, approaches, and creative evaluation tools. During this time the teacher tends to work to complete tasks and responsibilities, not in the stage of visionary thinking to create a learning system that is fun for students and in a critical paradigm. Referring to Barr's thought that Social Science (IPS) is a useful subject for discussing social problems and ongoing phenomena in society. The aim is to provide students with experience in social life. In the learning process, the teacher transmits knowledge and students dialogue with their friends in search of truth. ⁽⁶⁾

To teach controversial material oriented towards developing students' critical thinking and social analysis ability, teachers need to understand the theory of critical pedagogy. ^(7,8) This theory is one of the guidelines for teachers who make dialogue in the classroom as a power to develop students' abilities. Critical pedagogy aims to transform information about society through praxis which involves the articulation between theory and practice, thinking and doing. ⁽⁹⁾ The unity of theory and practice in critical pedagogy cannot be separated, so what is contained in the concept of critical pedagogy is not rhetorical, ⁽¹⁰⁾ but concrete actions that originate from world reality. In Giroux

paradigm, critical pedagogy leads to the humanization of students, ⁽⁷⁾ which is a process that is based on the idea that people need peace and mutual caring nature to live together. These characteristics in education process require the founding of strong knowledge related to critical thinking and the capacity to analyze social phenomena in society. Therefore, the implementation of the theory in this research is to see the extent to which the learning of controversy in social studies class is able to make students have awareness and concern for their social environment.

This research departs from Hess's argument which stated that the learning of controversial material in social studies is one of the keys to develop students' critical thinking and social analysis ability that will equip them with the knowledge to live in society. ⁽¹¹⁾ In Hess's explanation, outlining the problems regarding social studies teaching by the teacher, the most interesting thing to review is that the desire and capacity of the teacher to improvise the material being taught, the knowledge possessed will affect the creativity that is carried out. The next influential research in this article is the results of Malikow's study of the study of controversial material in the education of the social sciences, ⁽¹²⁾ according to him, a material in social science education certainly has a controversial side that can be discussed in dialogue, and therefore, this will lead to two possibilities, namely: opportunities or obstacles. Creative teachers will make it an opportunity, while conventional teachers will make it an obstacle in completing their responsibilities. Learning materials are ideal controversy can only be done by creative teachers who have the capacity to improvise in teaching.

Based on the explanation above, this research seeks to analyze the implementation of controversial learning material on social studies subjects in an effort to develop critical thinking and social analysis ability of students which conducted in secondary schools. Therefore, the

research question is: 1) how is the implementation of learning controversy in social studies class in an effort to develop students' critical thinking and social analysis ability?

MATERIALS & METHODS

Research Design

This research was conducted using Creswell's framework, namely the study of phenomenology in qualitative research. ⁽¹³⁾ The phenomenon in this study is the implementation of controversial learning material in social studies subjects in developing students' critical thinking and social analysis ability. The unit of phenomena in this study is specific and distinctive, both in terms of objects and supporting subjects, especially in the realm of social studies education research. One of the key points why this research was carried out using a phenomenological design is the effort of researchers to describe hidden experiences in the philosophical and psychological aspects of individuals that will be revealed through narration so that the audience can understand the actual condition of the research subject.

Data Collection

The data source of this research came from secondary school social studies teachers in Semarang as informants, both in the interview and observation sessions during the teacher's teaching. Informants were determined by purposive technique, namely the determination of informants is not based on guidelines or based on population representatives, but based on the depth of information needed, ^(14,15) by finding key informants who will then proceed with other informants with the aim of developing and finding as much information as possible related to the research problem.

Data Analysis

The data analysis activities in this research refers to the Creswell phenomenology data analysis framework, which explains the data

analysis techniques in phenomenology studies as follows: 1) The researcher fully describes the phenomena / experiences experienced by the research subjects; 2) The researcher then finds a statement (the results of the interview) about how people found the topic, detailed statements and the treatment of each statement has an equivalent value, then the details are developed with no repetition; 3) The statements are then grouped into meaningful units, the researcher breaks down the units and writes a text explanation of the experience accompanied by empirical evidence that explains the reality of the subject under study; 4) The researcher then reflects on his thinking by using imaginative variation or structural description, searching for all possible meanings and through divergent perspectives, making a consideration of the frame of reference for the phenomenon being studied, and constructing how the phenomenon is experienced; 5) The researchers then construct the whole explanation of the meaning and essence of his experience; and 6) The researcher reports the results of his research, the report compiled shows the existence of a unity of meaning based on the experience of all informants. After that, the researcher comprehensively writes the combined description. ⁽¹³⁾

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Learning controversy requires teacher initiative and students' readiness to be able to dialogue in class, ^(16,17) discussing discourse that is tucked in every controversy material in social studies. The controversy materials after factual analysis can be formulated as follows: 1) the entry of Hindu-Buddhism in Indonesia; 2) the entry of Islam in Indonesia; 3) 350 years of Dutch colonialism in Indonesia; 4) the September 30th Movement of the Indonesian Communist Party; 5) warrant of eleven march; 6) multiculturalism; 7) democratic economy; 8) poverty; and 9) processing of Natural Resources. All material mentioned are considered a controversy due to several

reasons, namely the version of the material, the content of the pros and cons that cover it, and expert arguments related to the material which are still in the process of debate. So that the material mentioned has met the criteria as controversy material in social studies, even though it is still very fragmented in the basis of certain social sciences. This also becomes a reflection that the social studies learning developed so far is still not ideal enough to internalize the values of citizenship, because the form and style of social studies that are developing are far from the true nature of social studies.

The implementation of the study of controversy material conducted by social studies teachers is still shackled by confusion about the definition of the material or the issues of controversy itself. Hess believed that controversy can be taught correctly if the teacher was able to understand anatomically the form of the material. (18,19) This opinion is in line with Ahmad's explanation that the controversy material is one of the discussion units in education whose teaching must involve the literacy process of the teacher, (8,20) this literacy activity aims to discover the anatomical form of the material. (21,22) The teacher's confusion regarding this material is illustrated in the following argument: "This controversy material is actually not in the composition of the material, so teaching it also cannot be done directly by preparing special learning tools, for me it is still confusing." (Siti Makrifatun, personal interview, February 20th, 2020). "For me the controversy in a material is reasonable, especially in history, but there are no specific guidelines regarding the teaching of the material so the teacher is still groping." (Orbani Imana, personal interview, February 23rd, 2020). Both opinions are reinforced by the following teacher's views: "Controversy material actually has a special characteristic that is there are pros and cons, but now it is difficult to implement because the composition of the material is too much so the teacher has a big burden." (Tutik Indarti, personal interview February 26th,

2020). The explanation conveyed was confirmed in the learning process carried out, in its implementation, the teacher was still hesitant in explaining the controversy material, the explanation was also not specific, this made the instructions given could not be captured strongly by students, so learning proceeded slowly and classes tended not responsive.

Actually, the teacher has a strong awareness in developing controversy material as learning material, various ways teachers are done to create quality learning material, especially in an effort to build critical understanding of students. Giroux argued that teacher insight greatly influences the process of internalizing knowledge to students. (23,24) In an effort to enrich insights related to controversial issues, the teacher did a variety of ways, one of the teachers argued the following: "If I am, the most important thing is not to focus on just one source, for example material on poverty, so I must read theories and reality of poverty." (Siti Makrifatun, personal interview, February 20th, 2020). The understanding conveyed is enough to illustrate that in an effort to develop controversy material, teachers have the initiative to enrich insights. This opinion is supported by the following opinion: "Now the era is all digital, if we need information, we just need to enter the search engine, so I strengthen the literacy ability and also utilize it, on the internet credible learning resources and resources are quite abundant." (Orbani Imana, personal interview, February 23rd, 2020). This finding is in line with Malikow's view that the literacy competence of a teacher greatly influences the understanding that will be formed in learning, including in the formation of understanding on controversial material. (12) The teacher is a catalyst that functions to connect the knowledge possessed by students and combine it with knowledge that comes from various sources, so that the understanding that will be constructed within students will be more optimal.

On observations made in the study of controversial material, teachers tend to conduct discussions based on the arrangement of material that is formally contained in the curriculum. Hess explained that the understanding that was built on the basis of curriculum formalism would only meet the needs of students' knowledge that was not widespread in the process of criticism and analytical. Knowledge of controversy material developed on the basis of such, will never arrive at the objectives of the learning of the material. ⁽¹¹⁾ This is reinforced by the following teacher's opinion: "If what is developed is essentially ordinary material, because there is no controversy in the curriculum design, so we also don't prepare too many needs." (Siti Makrifatun, personal interview, February 20th, 2020). In line with that the teacher also explained that: "for development, my material still refers to the book. But I always develop strategies." (Tutik Indiarti, personal interview February 26th, 2020). This explanation reinforces the findings that social studies learning so far are still shackled by the bondage of curriculum formalism, so that the development carried out is also not progressive enough, especially in the effort to internalize new knowledge to students. If taught conventionally, the controversy material is only ordinary material or even mere information, but the principle of teaching this controversy material requires the teacher to go further, especially in an effort to develop critical knowledge and social analysis of students. ^(9,25)

The process of analyzing the initial conditions of students prior to the implementation of the controversy material learning by social studies teachers does not seem to be as expected, this shows that the shackles of formalism faced by teachers are widespread, so learning is likely to have many obstacles. In the observations made, the teacher still stammered in starting the class and running the learning scheme according to what was written in the learning device. This is reinforced by the

teacher's following explanation: "So far, I have not seen the results of the analysis of the students' initial conditions as a reference in formulating a learning scheme, even though in the set up I wrote it is written that the initial conditions of learning are a reference in preparing learning." (Siti Makrifatun, personal interview, February 20th, 2020). This opinion is supported by the following argument: "if you must pay attention to the initial analysis of students, the learning time will run out, and learning preparation is not optimal because it requires a long time." (Orbani Imana, personal interview, February 23rd, 2020). This opinion is in line with Freire that efforts to develop the ability to think critically and social analysis cannot be carried out with the spirit of conventional teaching, even though the basics of learning itself can be applied, but learning with conventional principles will make teaching monotonous and boring. ⁽⁹⁾ This was proven after the confirmation process was carried out, learning with discussion schemes ran in an undirected direction and teachers tended to rely on unilateral delivery of information to calm the debate that was carried out, besides that the class is still dominated by certain students, who are habitus who have more activity than others, so that the class seems not to run democratically.

The lesson plan has not become the main reference and social studies teachers tend not consistent in carrying out the plan. So far, it can be said that the lesson plan is the formal basis of learning carried out, besides that the lesson plan is an administrative requirement that must be met by the teacher at the beginning of the semester, when in fact the teacher has the opportunity to innovate the lesson plan before learning is done, but the teacher does not pay attention to it because the teaching load of the teacher is already very large and can be said to be not proportional. This opinion is reinforced through the following teacher's explanation: "if the lesson plan is to be carried out consistently, it should reduce the teaching burden of the teacher

without reducing teacher rights, at this time our era is more burdened by administration than the burden of developing student knowledge." (Siti Makrifatun, personal interview, February 20th, 2020). This opinion is supported by the following teacher's explanation: "During this time, the lesson plan has become an administrative burden, indeed the aim is good so that the teacher can be improvised but in fact it becomes a burden." (Orbani Imana, personal interview, February 23rd, 2020). The explanation is a kind of aspiration that should be considered as input for the improvement of social studies education, such conditions strengthen the hypothesis that critical knowledge in the study of controversial material will be further from reality. Hess believes that the development of critical knowledge in learning controversy material must be done consequently from the learning planning process to the evaluation. ⁽¹¹⁾ All the processes that are passed are systematic learning that must be obeyed, without the fetter of teacher improvisation and innovation in learning. So the lesson plans that are prepared must be dynamic and applicable.

Social studies teachers already have a high sense of using technology in learning. Utilization of this technology, in Hess's view is very contextual with the effort to teach controversy material in social studies. ^(11, 26) Utilization of these technologies in general as a stimulus in facilitating students to develop their thinking power, more specifically supports the truth-seeking efforts that are carried out scientifically. ⁽²⁷⁻²⁹⁾ This autonomous formation of knowledge has greater potential in efforts to develop complex understanding, compared to the formation of directed knowledge. In relation to the use of various technologies, teachers have quite strong preferences, such as the use of quality websites, videos on YouTube, to social media that contains quite complex information. These observations are supported by the following teacher's opinion: "Learning this

controversial material can actually be done if access to the internet is quite open, whereas if I usually ask students to find as much data as possible from the internet so they understand the contextualization of the material being studied." (Siti Makrifatun, personal interview, February 20th, 2020). The opinion was reinforced by the following explanation: "I fixed the initiative to explain to the students, and the students also explored independent information through the internet, so far it is quite influential in efforts to form a student's knowledge." (Tutik Indiarti, personal interview, February 26th, 2020). This finding suggests that critical and analytical student knowledge development efforts can be supported by the wise use of technology in the learning process of the controversial material.

Students are born with various kinds of potential that can be developed at school. On the controversy of learning material, the potential that can be developed is the critical thinking skills in problem solving and analyzing social phenomena in society. The ability of these students is influenced in large part by the reading material they have, and other literacy activities such as dialogue, listening to podcasts related to lessons, and viewing video shows related to the material are factors that make the formation of student knowledge run optimally. Related to the development of students' ability to solve problems teachers argue that: "the ability of participants in each individual class is different, there are those who immediately understand when the teacher explains the first time, and there are also those who must be guided slowly, the key is the teacher must continue to consistently develop student knowledge and patience in guiding." (Siti Makrifatun, personal interview, February 20th, 2020). Strengthening these opinions the teacher explained that: "the controversy material has enough impact, namely the ability of students to solve problems, they are enthusiastic if the material being taught contains pros and cons." (Orbani Imana, personal interview, February 23rd, 2020).

The teacher also gives an opinion which shows that the literacy ability of students is difficult to develop, that: "students today have little interest in reading. Though Social Science (IPS) must read a lot. Students also sometimes difficult to be conditioned." (Tutik Indarti, personal interview, February 26th, 2020). Hess believes that learning controversial material can be worked on to help attract students' interest in learning, (18) in addition to the interest of students who are already interested in participating in learning, the teacher will be easy to condition the class, besides that the teacher can also use the ability of active students to stimulate other students who are not yet active in learning. The ability to operate classrooms is key in the formation of students' knowledge and skills.

Parker explained that the effort to develop an active and democratic classroom is a social learning agenda that includes an effort to develop students' critical thinking and social analysis ability. (30) Students who are active and democratic will make learning work ideally. (1, 31) This is a challenge for social studies teachers who currently do not seem to stand out as a special agenda. Difficulty in controlling class is considered as one of the problems which until now has not been resolved, the result is the teacher sometimes chooses shortcuts to apply lecture methods that tend to be repressive and anti-dialogue. In this context, the hypothesis is supported by the following teacher factual statement: "For student activity, almost all of them are active and enthusiastic in learning, but sometimes students are difficult to control, so I prefer the lecture method as a solution." (Siti Makrifatun, personal interview, February 20th, 2020). In addition, the teacher also argues that: "the lecture method is already inappropriate, but if we find it difficult to control the class, rather than learning to stop, I better fill it with lecture, usually in learning in the afternoon or evening." (Tutik Indarti, personal interview, February 26th, 2020). This finding is confirmed in the observation, that

social studies learning carried out by teachers is still largely dominated by teachers through lectures, whereas in the effort to develop knowledge, what must be emphasized is dialogue. However, it can be said that dialogue is not the teacher's priority in teaching.

Learning approaches that can be used in teaching controversial matter, if it refers Hess is a humanist approach. (18) Correspondingly, Giroux argues that the humanist approach can be utilized to realize a democratic classroom and foster students' critical thinking and social analysis abilities. (7) This is very relevant to the learning effort of controversy that enables dialogue in the classroom. The dialogue is a process of exchanging opinions related to the findings was found based on the results of students' independent exploration. In this context the teacher argues that: "It should be a humanist approach if it wants to create active and democratic learning, but it is very difficult in practice, especially in the afternoon teaching hours." (Siti Makrifatun, personal interview, February 20th, 2020). Learning and teaching hours are very influential in the process of determining the learning approach. The teacher considers teaching hours to be a benchmark for choosing the approach to be applied. However, in teaching the teacher has tried to apply a humanist approach, especially in the subject of poverty controversies, the use of natural resources, and people's economy. Strengthening the previous opinion the teacher explained that: "I agree with the humanist approach, because this approach gives a good position to students, especially students in learning is also positioned as a learning subject." (Orbani Imana, personal interview, February 23rd, 2020). Opinions that have been expressed reinforce the hypothesis that learning controversy with the humanist approach breeds democratic classrooms and places students in the position of learners who have great autonomous rights in developing their knowledge. (10, 12)

The implementation of controversial learning material is supported by PBL and Discovery Learning models which are applied by the teacher to stimulate the class so that it can run dialogically. Giroux argues that one model that greatly impacts the process of students' critical thinking and social analysis skills is a problem solving model that can dynamically be applied in learning. ⁽⁷⁾ Problem solving is one of the abilities that can be explored in social studies learning, the results of the learning process with this model also have a positive impact on students. In this context the teacher believes that: "I usually use Discovery Learning and PBL. Both models are very relevant for learning controversy, because basically controversy is a problem that must be solved." (Siti Makrifatun, personal interview, February 20th, 2020). This explanation is supported by the following teacher's opinion: "Problem solving models are very relevant, because students can work together in discussing a problem, this controversy material has the potential to give birth to dialectics in the classroom." (Orbani Imana, personal interview, February 23rd, 2020). In the confirmation process of implementing learning, the teacher consistently implements these models as a teaching scheme on controversial material.

Barr argued that learning resources that can be utilized in an effort to develop critical thinking skills and social analysis of students in social studies learning are various kinds of texts from reliable sources such as articles and books. ⁽³²⁾ In the present context, Parker completes the explanation that the current learning resources of social science materials can be obtained from digital access, not just print such as books and mass media. ⁽³⁰⁾ Social studies teachers have in principle made sources such as articles, videos, and books as student learning materials. This was confirmed in the observation of the implementation of learning and was confirmed through the results of the interview that: "for learning resources we also open the internet and

sometimes if I read a newspaper or magazine that includes the material I bring with me then I discuss it in class." (Siti Makrifatun, personal interview, February 20th, 2020). In addition, the teacher also argues that: "Of course at the moment there are a lot of learning resources, I often bring a number of journal articles in digital or soft files for discussion in class. Students are very interested, especially when it comes to controversy." (Orbani Imana, personal interview, February 23rd, 2020). This explanation is reinforced by the following opinion: "Books, journal articles, videos from YouTube, and articles on social media are important sources of learning, and I apply them all to strengthen students' knowledge." (Tutik Indarti, personal interview, February 26th, 2020). This explanation is in line with Sekarini that the learning of controversy material should be supported by diverse learning resources, ⁽³³⁾ efforts to develop students' critical thinking skills and social analysis are not sufficiently carried out by utilizing sober resources and containing limited information.

Ahmad explained that the controversy material would be more effectively taught with innovative media. ⁽²⁰⁾ These media such as info graphics, digital posters, digital maps, video documentaries, power points that are equipped with images, and besides that there is also the surrounding environment as a contextual media in learning. The application of innovative media in learning has a large impact on the formation of students' critical knowledge. This is in line with Myers' opinion that digital media in the era of globalization is the most relevant learning media, these media appear as criticisms of print media or physical form media which are quite difficult to obtain today. ⁽³⁴⁾ The most relevant and the most popular media right now are infographics and documentary videos. Both of these media proved able to arouse students' interest in studying social studies, because they could clearly describe the object being studied. Correspondingly, the results of confirmation in the

implementation of learning showed that teachers were able to utilize the media mentioned in combination, so students were quite enthusiastic in participating in learning. This finding was reinforced through the following teacher's opinion: "if the controversy material should be taught with innovative media, if I prefer to open classes with documentary videos to lead students to look for other relevant sources." (Siti Makrifatun, personal interview, February 20th, 2020). This opinion was in line with the teacher's explanation below: "The media used are digital because it is practical, if I, now prefer to provide stimulation through infographics or posters before learning controversy material goes into its key roll." (Orbani Imana, personal interview, February 23rd, 2020). The explanation given by the teacher is a mirror, the competence of social studies teachers in utilizing learning media. In addition, teachers also had a creative tendency to package learning based on digital media. The use of digital media has attracted students' interest and made the class more active in expressing the results of students' thinking individually or in groups.

From a series of learning implementation processes, assessment is one of the most important stages to find out to what extent the knowledge provided by the teacher and developed in the classroom can be well received by students. Barr argued that before the final assessment, ⁽⁶⁾ learning must first pay attention to the process of summative assignment to test students' understanding of the material being taught. Hess explained that the summative assessment process can be carried out by giving projects to students, related to the learning of controversial material, students can be directed to find out as much information as possible related to the topic being discussed, then students give an analysis of the findings they have obtained. ⁽¹¹⁾ In connection with the assignment, the planning of the teacher gives more assignments in the form of projects as explained by Hess above, the

project, if the learning material is controversial then it is analytic and information gathering. This is proven consistently in the implementation of learning. Project assignments are intended to familiarize students with analytical and critical thinking, especially related to controversy material. This is as explained by the teacher as follows: "The assignment that I give to students is usually in the form of projects, because that way, students can solve problems. Especially in controversial material, the assignments given will train students to think analytically." (Siti Makrifatun, personal interview, February 20th, 2020). Accordingly, the teacher believes that: "the assignment of assignments in the form of projects in the learning of controversial material has the aim of getting students used to solving problems and facing challenges, so students will get used to behaving." (Orbani Imana, personal interview, February 23rd, 2020). Assignments given are usually reported in portfolios done in groups, but each individual must remain actively involved in the process of working on the project. This is so that the learning that took place is still oriented on the achievement of predetermined objectives.

Evaluation is a series of activities aimed to measure the success of the education program. ⁽³⁵⁾ Whereas Barr in this case further reviews the understanding of program evaluation in the context of objectives, namely as a process of assessing the extent to which educational goals can be achieved. ⁽³⁾ The purpose of evaluation of learning is to gather information that is used as a basis for knowing the level of progress, development, and achievement of student learning, as well as the effectiveness of teacher teaching. Learning evaluation includes measurement and assessment activities. The characteristic of social studies education is its efforts to develop competencies as good citizens. A good citizen means one who can maintain harmonious relations between people so that national unity and integrity can be

established. Factually, the evaluation model that has been applied by the teacher to measure the achievement of learning objectives that have been determined is oral and written. The determination of the evaluation model is based on the reasons for strengthening and analyzing students' social analysis and critical thinking abilities. This is also illustrated in the following teacher's view: "the form of evaluation that I do is oral and written, the aim is to see the extent to which students' abilities are explored in learning, bearing in mind that each student only has strength in one aspect of evaluation." (Siti Makrifatun, personal interview, February 20th, 2020). Correspondingly, the teacher also argues that: "these two forms of evaluation are actually to create justice in the learning process carried out, each individual is usually strong in one aspect but in another aspect they are weak." (Tutik Indarti, personal interview, February 26th, 2020). Teachers already have good vision related to the achievement of learning objectives and the process of creating justice in their lessons. The evaluation model that is the findings and arguments that have been given is only a small part, in a more global process teachers have tried to "become" a true Social Studies (IPS) educator with the efforts they have done, one of which is strengthening literacy competencies from various sources. This also prepare and strengthen the analytical and critical understanding of the formation of the students in learning the material controversy that became one of the materials that are challenging for teachers. ⁽³⁶⁾ Specifically, social studies teachers are quite progressive in preparing learning plans, but in the process various obstacles were encountered as challenges that had to be solved, some teacher informants had taken initiatives to solve those problems. It was merely to make a better implementation of social studies learning and achievement of learning running optimally.

CONCLUSION

Learning controversy issues conducted by social studies teachers in terms of planning, implementation, and evaluation already meet the standards of learning implementation as outlined in the curriculum. It needed to be underlined in the process of developing critical thinking and social analysis abilities of students, so far the teacher still had a tendency to do learning with a one-way lecture approach and did not prioritize dialectics in teaching, so that the development of knowledge in the process was very weak and even in some cases made students' experience boredom in learning. Boredom in learning was also influenced by the choice of methods, approaches, and learning media. Some teachers were still unable to improvise the learning instruments used, or teachers still tend to act conventionally and regard teaching assignments as responsibilities that can be completed without having to take creative ways. This reflected that social studies learning required innovation and that could be started from strengthening the capacity of social studies teachers, especially in efforts to develop critical thinking and social analysis abilities of students who had not been endorsed and were still hindered by formal demands in implementing teaching.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT(S)

The researcher would like to express the sincerest gratitude to the Promoters Team who have published the results of this research as well as help improve the results of the analysis of the research themes that are raised. The most researcher's appreciation and gratitude also go to the Doctor of Social Sciences Education Study Program, Postgraduate Program, Universitas Negeri Semarang, for providing support so that this research article can be published.

REFERENCES

1. Sholeh B. Pengembangan Pembelajaran Pada Mata Pelajaran IPS Ekonomi Pada Siswa SMP Menggunakan Pendekatan Critical Pedagogy (The Development of Learning and Teaching Process of Social

- Subject of Economics In Junior High School Students Through Critical Pedagogy Approach). PEKOBIS: Jurnal Pendidikan, EKonomi, dan Bisnis. 2017;1(1).
2. King SSMB, Newmann FM, Carmichael DL. Authentic intellectual work: Common standards for teaching social studies. In: Social Studies Today. Routledge; 2015. p. 63–74.
 3. Barr R, Barth JL, Shermis SS. The nature of the social studies. ETC; 1978.
 4. Hess DE. Controversies about controversial issues in democratic education. PS: Political Science & Politics. 2004;37(2):257–261.
 5. Philpott S, Clabough J, McConkey L, Turner TN. Controversial issues: To teach or not to teach? That is the question. The Georgia Social Studies Journal. 2011;1(1): 32–44.
 6. Barr RD, Barth JL, Shermis SS. Defining the social studies. National Council for the Social Studies Washington, DC; 1977.
 7. Giroux HA. On critical pedagogy. Bloomsbury Publishing; 2020.
 8. Ahmad TA. Pembelajaran Sejarah Dalam Perspektif Critical Pedagogy. Semarang: Historia Pedagogia; 2012.
 9. Freire P. Pedagogy of the oppressed. Bloomsbury publishing USA; 2018.
 10. Giroux HA, Freire P, McLaren P. Teachers as intellectuals: Toward a critical pedagogy of learning. Greenwood Publishing Group; 1988.
 11. Hess DE. Controversy in the classroom: The democratic power of discussion. Routledge; 2009.
 12. Malikow M. Engaging students in controversial issues. Kappa Delta Pi Record. 2006;42(3):106–108.
 13. Creswell JW, Poth CN. Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches. Sage publications; 2016.
 14. Yin RK. Case study research and applications: Design and methods. Sage publications; 2017.
 15. Gall M, Borg W, Gall J. Quantitative and qualitative methods of research in psychology and educational science. Nasr A, Arizi H, Abolghasemi M, Pakseresht MJ, Kiamanesh A, Bagheri Kh, et al(Persian translator) 1th edition Tehran: Samt. 2003;189–190.
 16. Adler S. 18. The education of social studies teachers. Handbook of research in social studies education. 2008;329–351.
 17. Byford J, Lennon S, Russell WB. Teaching controversial issues in the social studies: A research study of high school teachers. The Clearing House: A Journal of Educational Strategies, Issues and Ideas. 2009;82(4): 165–170.
 18. Hess D. Controversial issues and democratic discourse. Handbook of research in social studies education. 2008;124–136.
 19. Hess DE. Discussing controversial public issues in secondary social studies classrooms: Learning from skilled teachers. Theory & Research in Social Education. 2002;30(1):10–41.
 20. Ahmad TA. Sejarah Kontroversial Di Indonesia: Perspektif Pendidikan. Yayasan Pustaka Obor Indonesia; 2016.
 21. Brophy J, Alleman J, Halvorsen A-L. Powerful social studies for elementary students. Cengage Learning; 2016.
 22. Asimeng-Boahene L. Creating strategies to deal with problems of teaching controversial issues in social studies education in African schools. Intercultural Education. 2007; 18(3): 231–242.
 23. Giroux HA, McLaren P. Between borders: Pedagogy and the politics of cultural studies. Routledge; 2014.
 24. Giroux HA. Border crossings: Cultural workers and the politics of education. Psychology Press; 1992.
 25. Giroux HA, McLaren P. Paulo Freire, postmodernism and the utopian imagination: a Blochian reading. 1997;
 26. Tambunan N, Batubara FA. Gadget Utilization as a Source of Learning Students of Grade XII SMA Panca Budi Medan.
 27. Bolick CM, Berson M, Coutts C, Heinecke W. Technology applications in social studies teacher education: A survey of social studies methods faculty. Contemporary issues in technology and teacher education. 2003;3(3):300–309.
 28. Suwirta A. Mengkritisi Peristiwa G30S 1965: Dominasi Wacana Sejarah Orde Baru dalam Sorotan” dalam HISTORIA: Jurnal Pendidikan Sejarah, Vol. 1 (1), Juni, hlm. 43-49. Bandung: Jurusan Pendidikan Sejarah FPIPS UPI [Fakultas Pendidikan Ilmu Pengetahuan Sosial, Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia]. 2000;
 29. Romadi R, Kurniawan GF. Pembelajaran Sejarah Lokal Berbasis Folklore Untuk Menanamkan Nilai Kearifan Lokal Kepada Siswa. Sejarah dan Budaya: Jurnal Sejarah,

- Budaya, dan Pengajarannya. 2017;11(1):79–94.
30. Parker W. Social Studies in Elementary Education, 14/e. Pearson Education India; 2009.
31. Enyiaka JU, Aminigo IM, Osaat SD. Basis of Civic Education in the Philosophy of Aristotle: A Nigerian Reflection.
32. Barr R, Barth JL, Shermis SS. The nature of the social studies. ETC; 1978.
33. Sekarini I. Penguunaan Metode Problem Solving Untuk Peningkatan Keaktifan Peserta Didik Dalam Diskusi Kelompok Pada Kajian Isu Kontroversial Pembelajaran Ips (Penelitian Tindakan Kelas di Kelas VII-K SMP Negeri 10 Bandung) [PhD Thesis]. Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia; 2016.
34. Myers JP. Rethinking the social studies curriculum in the context of globalization: Education for global citizenship in the US. Theory & Research in Social Education. 2006;34(3):370–394.
35. Parker A, Tritter J. Focus group method and methodology: current practice and recent debate. International Journal of Research & Method in Education. 2006;29(1):23–37.
36. Maftuh B. Internalisasi nilai-nilai Pancasila dan nasionalisme melalui pendidikan kewarganegaraan. Jurnal Educationist. 2008; 2(2):134–144.

How to cite this article: Purnomo A, Wasino, Astuti TMP et.al. Teaching controversial issues in social studies class to develop critical thinking and social analysis ability. International Journal of Research and Review. 2020; 7(6): 371-382.
